

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: SALL2.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of SALL2 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human
11 embryonic stem cell.

12 Citations

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